

ORACULAR REASONING: THE LIMITS OF JUSTIFIED BELIEF IN GETTIER-TYPE ARGUMENTS ABOUT KNOWLEDGE.

ALEJANDRO MATUS

Abstract. Through logical analysis, we demonstrate how Gettier cases, presented as counterexamples to the conception of knowledge as justified true belief, are not syntactically valid, as they are a variation of oracular reasoning, a logical fallacy where the specific interpreted propositions, which contain a logical constant, are confused with propositions formed by uninterpreted logical variables, ambiguous; "there is one and only one" is mixed-up with "there exists some", necessary and sufficient conditions with necessary but not sufficient conditions; and there are cognitive biases, for instance, the neglect of base rates in the argumentation.

Keywords: EPISTEMOLOGY _ FALLACIES _ LOGIC _ NECESSITY AND SUFFICIENCY _ TRUTH _ BIAS _ DEDUCTION AND EXPERIENCE _ QUANTIFIERS _ FREQUENCIES _ TVERSKY _ GETTIER.

Against the conception of knowledge as justified true belief, Edmund L. Gettier proposed two cases as counterexamples. This has had a significant impact among scholars in the field of Epistemology, where the stipulation of such counterexamples has even multiplied.

It is widely conceived that these cases are logically valid arguments, necessitating a correction in the aforementioned characterization of knowledge, either by modifying or expanding the conditions to describe it (cf. Dretske 1971; Goldman 1976; Nozick 1981, pp. 178-180; Lycan 2006).

In this article, we conduct an analysis to show that these counterexamples have logical flaws that prevent them from being valid. These flaws essentially consist of a type of reasoning very similar to that found in many oracular predictions and astrological forecasts, where concrete propositions that contain logical constants are confused with propositions composed of uninterpreted, abstract, logical variables; logical quantifiers of uniqueness with mere existence quantifiers; necessary and sufficient conditions with necessary but not sufficient conditions; and the base frequency rates also are confused.

To exhibit such structural similarity, we first analyze what constitutes oracular reasoning; and from there, its erroneous logical structure. Then, we apply the results to the two cases presented by Gettier, which depend on logical deductions, and analyze how such consequences also apply to subsequent cases generated by other authors, related to empirical knowledge. We focus on how the forms of justifying a belief can be exhausted (by logical deduction or direct or indirect experience). Finally, we outline in general terms the deep and fallacious structure of the procedure.

1. Oracular reasoning.

Herodotus recounts: Some Lydians

were charged by Croesus (his king) to inquire to the oracles, "Shall Croesus send an army against the Persians?". ... The judgment

given to Croesus was that if he should send an army against the Persians he would destroy a great empire. ... (Croesus) was greatly pleased with the oracles ... fully persuaded that he would destroy the kingdom of Cyrus ... And so led his army to the Persian territory.

Croesus was defeated.

As the oracle foretold, brought his own great empire to an end.

Cyrus allowed him to send other emissaries

To ask if the god [Apollo] were not ashamed that he had persuaded Croesus to attack the Persians, telling him that he would destroy Cyrus' power; ... The priestess (it is said) thus replied: ... Croesus doth not right to complain concerning it. For Loxias declared to him that if he should lead an army against the Persians he would destroy a great empire. Therefore it behoved him, if he would take right counsel, to send and ask whether the god spoke of Croesus' or of Cyrus' empire. But he understood not that which was spoken, nor made further inquiry: wherefore now let him blame himself (Herodotus. Book I, 53-54, 75, 86, 90-91).

In the end, Croesus accepted this replica.

2. The logical structure of oracular reasoning.

This prophecy is a clear example of a large number of oracular and astrological predictions, with a logical structure of the following type:

- a) The prophet issues an *ambiguous* proposition, that is, a general proposition that admits more than one specification as an option.
- b) Someone, typically the recipient of the prediction, *specifies* this proposition, giving it a univocal meaning, usually corresponding to personal past experiences, biases, and hopes.
- c) If that particular option occurs in reality, the oracle claims to have been correct. If it does not occur, the oracle evades responsibility by attributing an erroneous *specification* to the inquirer. The diviner asserts that what he meant was the specific option that indeed occurred, which is, of course, consistent with the generality of the prediction.

We can analyze this in formal logical terms:

a') The augur emits a sentence which can be expressed as a propositional function with a *variable* x that can take more than one value; and not a *specific* sentence that can be expressed as a statement that gives x a constant value. The seer handles his sentence without can be specified what x is equal to. He simply asserts Fx .

b') It is the interested party who assigns a value to x , usually without realizing that such a role has been left to him, assuming that this interpretative specification is implicit in the prophet's utterance. Thus, the interested party believes they have been provided not Fx , but for example, Fa , with $x=a$.

c') If Fa occurs, the oracle is considered correct ($Fx \equiv Fa$), by both the questioner and the seer. If $x \neq a$ occurs, the augur attributes the error to the questioner; and if, furthermore, $x=b$, and therefore Fb , he asserts that that was what he meant

$(Fx \equiv Fb)$ and thus he was correct. Frequently, the questioner ends up accepting that response.

The structure of the fallacy consists of issuing an ambiguity, the equivalent to a propositional function, but improperly considering it (from a logical standpoint) as if it were itself the equivalent of an interpreted formula, more specific than it actually is. It takes advantage of the fact that the function has more than one option for concretization, but treats it as if it were a single option in itself. It allows a specific value to be assigned and does not object to that value until the concrete fact occurs that makes it true or false.

If it is true, the propositional function is deemed validated.

If it is false, the falsehood is allowed to fall back on the first formula already taken as a particular option. But there is an implicit recourse to a second specific option, which corresponds to the fact that actually occurred. And it is believed or claimed that when emitting the propositional function, what was meant was the new determination.

Initially, it is assumed that both the propositional function and its first specified formula have the same validity. Later, it is taken as identical the same propositional function and a second formula, specified differently from the first, and contradictory to it.

3. Gettier's Argumentation. First Case.

Next, we will apply what has been said to Gettier's reasoning.

He famously asks, "Is knowledge justified true belief?" (Gettier, 1963), addressing a conception of various epistemologists (cf. Plato, *Meno* 97a-98b and *Theaetetus* 200d-210c; Ayer, 1956, p. 34; Chisholm, 1957, p. 16), according to which the necessary and sufficient conditions for someone to know a given proposition are:

1. The proposition P is true;
2. S believes that P; and
3. S is justified in believing that P.

Gettier argues that such a conception is false, as he can formulate counterexamples to it.

He proposes the following:

Suppose that Smith and Jones have applied for a certain job. And suppose that Smith has strong evidence for the following conjunctive proposition:
 d. Jones is the man who will get the job, and Jones has ten coins in his pocket. ... Proposition (d) entails:
 e. The man who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket.
 Let us suppose that Smith sees the entailment from (d) to (e), and accepts (e) on the grounds of (d), for which he has strong evidence. In this case, Smith is clearly justified in believing that (e) is true. ... But imagine, further, that unknown to Smith, he himself, not Jones, will get the job. And, also, unknown to Smith, he himself has ten coins in his pocket. Proposition (e) is then true, though proposition

(d), from which Smith inferred (e), is false. In our example, then, all of the following are true: (i) (e) is true, (ii) Smith believes that (e) is true, and (iii) Smith is justified in believing that (e) is true. But it is equally clear that Smith does not *know* that (e) is true; for (e) is true in virtue of the number of coins in Smith's pocket, while Smith does not know how many coins are in Smith's pocket, and bases his belief in (e) on a count of the coins in Jones's pocket, whom he falsely believes to be the man who will get the job (Gettier 1963).

Let us analyze this counterexample:

The proposition (d) corresponds to an expression of the type

$\exists x: x=j \wedge Tx \wedge Mx.$

Where j =Jones; T = Will get the job; M = Has ten coins in his pocket.

Here x has taken the value of an individual constant, which always has the value of j . It refers to a specific individual who fulfills the conditions stipulated in the description. Although (e) is derived from (d), Gettier's argument sets aside that (e) is a non-specific sentence (i.e., corresponds to a propositional function). Only when one has opted for a specific constant with $x=a$, or $x=b$, or $x=s$, or $x=j$, etc., as in (d), does it become a particularized formula, interpreted, to which a truth or falsity value can be assigned regarding a single concrete object, a single option.

Thus, in (e), Gettier takes x as if it were a still indeterminate variable, which can take on values other than j . And he derives from this a new value of x , when it happens that "Smith" is the specific value that makes (e) true. This implicitly generates a new determined proposition (f). And by doing this, he is actually performing a new operation, in which $(e) \rightarrow (f)$, by substitution of the variable x with the new constant s ($\neq j$). With (f):

f) The man, Smith, who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket.

Assigning to x , "The man", the value of "Smith".

Instead of the expression derived from the original:

e') The man, Jones, who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket.

Which assigns to the variable x , "The man", the value of "Jones".

In other words, this concerns a *confusion* in logical *quantifiers*; the difference between "There exists one and only one x " (which predicates the existence and uniqueness of an object, and can exclusively be, for example, $x=j$, which assigns x a specific constant value), and "There exists some x " (which predicates only existence, and can be $x=a$ or $x=b$ or $x=j$, etc.).

More precisely, (d) can be syntactically formulated as

d') $\exists!x: x=j \wedge Tj \wedge Mj.$

Where $E!$ = There is one and only one.

Since this description formally includes the logical assertion that the individual exclusively possesses the characteristics attributed to him, and that no other individual possesses them, in addition to existence, it predicates uniqueness: that there is only one object that fulfills those characteristics (cf. Russell 1905).

Thus we have, equivalently:

d") $\exists x \forall y (Hx \wedge Tx \wedge Mx \wedge (Ty \wedge My \rightarrow y=x) \wedge x=j)$

That is, there is an x such that x is a man (H), who is going to get the job (T), and that man has ten cents in his pocket (M); and if any man (y) gets the job, and that man has ten cents in his pocket, that man is Jones.

The part bound $\forall y (Ty \wedge My \rightarrow y=x)$ excludes any other individual distinct from Jones fulfilling the necessary and sufficient conditions expressed by proposition P .

(d') is what Smith believes he knows. That if there is a man referred to as " y " (for instance, "the man with black hair" or "the man in the brown shirt" or "the man with green eyes" or "the man with ten coins in his pocket"), and that man gets the job, that man is Jones ($Ty \rightarrow y=x$).

In his argument, by entailing (e), Gettier validly sets aside the necessary condition ($Ty \wedge My \rightarrow x=y$). However, in (e), Gettier uses "The man" as a variable that can be replaced by any of a set of alternative constants, by several options, when in reality in (d) there occurs a unique option, one and only one defined logical constant.

In other words, Gettier first replaces the particular with the general. He transforms a specific proposition Fj about Jones into a proposition Fx about a possible individual who may or may not be Jones, but which comes from the assumption that he is Jones.

But then, inadvertently and fallaciously, as in an oracular reasoning, he converts this Fx into a new proposition Fs , now about another constant: Smith.

What Gettier does is assign a new specific value to the variable x based on the propositional function (e), that of $x=s$, inadvertently generating a new proposition (f) distinct from (d) and (e), contradictory to (d), in an unjustified step.

And this option (f), but not the one Smith believes he knows, (e), is the specific formula option, the proposition, that Gettier ultimately adopts, which is true or false based on whether the job is assigned or not solely to Smith, to s ; while the more general option (e) may be true when the job is assigned either to Smith or to Jones, or to any other person with ten coins in their pocket. That is, both to Smith and not Smith, to s as well as to $\neg s$; to Jones, or not Jones, to j as well as to $\neg j$.

The meaning of (e) for Smith's belief always presupposes Jones. "The man who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket" always means "Jones" to Smith and is therefore modally never substitutable for "Smith" or anyone else. The issue is not about the mere proposition, but about Smith's *belief* regarding the proposition.

It is false that Smith justifiably believes that (e) without prior univocity. What Gettier achieves is a fallacious change of constant regarding (d), forming (f); and he confuses (e) with (f). Therefore, his Smith is not logically justified in believing that P is true under any specification option.

In the case of Croesus, with either of the two options that arise, the priests will be able to say that the Pythia was right. What occurred is that she issued a type (e) sentence, with a non-specific propositional function structure, ambiguous, with more than one option, without assigning a defined value to x. And it was subsequently, implicitly, without realizing it, that Croesus himself fallaciously substituted the x for the constant of his liking or bias ("Persia"); and after the events, the oracle substituted it with the constant "Lydia"; just as Gettier takes in (d) the x as "Jones" and then in (f) substitutes from (e) the x for "Smith."

4. Necessary and Sufficient Conditions.

The condition "One and only one" emphasizes the need to establish the necessary and sufficient conditions to specify that particular one. In addition to the general necessary and sufficient conditions for knowledge to exist, in the specific case presented by Gettier, it is necessary and sufficient for knowledge about Smith that the particular conditions of existence and uniqueness are met:

1. Jones is the person who will get the job,
2. There exists one and only one person who will get the job; and
3. Jones has ten coins in his pocket.

From the logical perspective of the specific knowledge that Smith may have, these three are the necessary and sufficient conditions determined by (d) for him to know that P. When he deduces (e) from (d), he eliminates one of those conditions, the main one, which is $E!x:x=j$; thus (e) no longer expresses the sufficient conditions in this specific case for Smith to believe that (d).

When Gettier only takes two of the three conditions in (e) and excludes the one where $x=$ Jones, he can only validly deduce, not oracularly, that Smith knows that those two conditions are *necessary, but not sufficient* to specify who will get the job. However, Gettier erroneously reasons as if for Smith those two reasons were sufficient.

By assuming that (1), (2), and (3) are necessary and sufficient reasons to claim that Smith believes P, Gettier fallaciously moves to assume that (2) and (3), excluding (1), are necessary and sufficient reasons to assert that Smith believes proposition P. When the valid conclusion is merely that (2) and (3) are necessary reasons, but not sufficient (since (1) with $x=j$ is missing) to assert that Smith believes P. Thus, one of the necessary conditions to say that Smith believes P has not been met. To truthfully assert that Smith believes P, it is necessary that $\exists x:Tx \wedge Mx$, but it is not sufficient. It is also necessary that $x=j$.

Then, Gettier moves from

Smith believes P \leftrightarrow (1), (2), and (3) (i.e., P *if and only if* $\exists!x:x=j \wedge Tx \wedge Mx$),

to (tacitly)

Smith believes P \leftrightarrow (2) and (3) (i.e., P *if and only if* $\exists x:Tx \wedge Mx$).

He incorrectly (and implicitly) maintains the "if and only if."

When what is syntactically justified is only

Smith believes P \rightarrow (2) and (3) (i.e., that P *entails* $\exists x:Tx \wedge Mx$).

That is, with simple implication, but no longer with the biconditional.

Therefore, if Smith reasons in a logically coherent manner, he cannot believe that (e) is true if he presumes those necessary reasons as sufficient. Or, if he believes that with such a presumption (e) is true, then he is not logically justified in believing such a thing. As he is justified in believing that (e) is true if he presumes those reasons as necessary, but not sufficient.

In summary, Gettier presents (e), which has the structure of a propositional function, based on (d) — with (d) as an interpreted formula. But the option expressed by (d) does not occur; instead, it is the one expressed by another specified formula (f), that is different. Subtly, Gettier re-specifies (e), now based on the fact actually happening, according to his approach (as expressed by the interpreted formula (f)).

And he improperly attributes the belief in the truth of this new specification (f) to the sentence (e), the propositional function from which it originates, and not only, as logically corresponds, to the new interpreted formula (f).

It is as if G, an amateur cook, wanted to apply the recipe for a dessert from a renowned chef that specifies:

d) Add cinnamon (cf. with "The empire of Cyrus is going to fall"; or "Jones is the man who will get the job and has ten coins in his pocket").

But G did not have cinnamon available at that moment, and deduced that as (d) implies the generalization:

e) Add a spice (cf. "A great empire is going to fall"; or "The man who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket"),

then he can

f) Add pepper since it is also a spice (cf. "The empire of Croesus is going to fall"; or "The man (Smith) who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket").

And by doing so, the dessert would taste bad. And therefore, he might conclude that the recipe is actually bad, ... and not his way of understanding logic.

5. The second case of Gettier.

Gettier states:

Let us suppose that Smith has strong evidence for the following proposition:

f. Jones owns a Ford. ...

Smith has another friend, Brown, of whose whereabouts he is totally ignorant. Smith selects three place names quite at random and constructs the following three propositions:

g. Either Jones owns a Ford, or Brown is in Boston.

h. Either Jones owns a Ford, or Brown is in Barcelona.

i. Either Jones owns a Ford, or Brown is in Brest-Litovsk.

... Imagine that Smith ... proceeds to accept (g), (h), and (i) on the basis of (f). ... Smith is therefore completely justified in believing each of these three propositions ... But imagine now that two further conditions hold. First Jones does not own a Ford, but is at present driving a rented car. And secondly, by the sheerest coincidence, and entirely unknown to Smith, the place mentioned in proposition (h) happens really to be the place where Brown is. If these two conditions hold, then Smith does not know that (h) is true, even though (i) (h) is true, (ii) Smith does believe that (h) is true, and (iii) Smith is justified in believing that (h) is true (Gettier, 1963).

In this case, Gettier merely chooses three specific propositions for his disjunctions, from an infinite pool of possibilities. From (f), Smith forms three sentences of the form $(f) \vee X$ (with X being a variable proposition), among them (h), where he substitutes X with B: "Brown is in Barcelona".

However, one can also form an infinite number of other statements by substituting X with other sentences, such as,

(h*): either Jones owns a Ford or Brown is NOT in Barcelona.

Where $X = \neg B$, that is, it results in $(f) \vee \neg B$. It can be justifiably believed that all those propositions are true, as (f) is true. Then, whether B or $\neg B$ occurs, even if (f) is false, the propositional formula $(f) \vee X$ will always be true (since B or $\neg B$ exhausts the universe of possible options), due to any of those occurrences that happen to be true concerning the variable X. Thus, while Smith justifiably believes that

(h) either Jones owns a Ford or Brown is in Barcelona,
he simultaneously justifiably believes that

(h*) either Jones owns a Ford or Brown is NOT in Barcelona.

Then, whether Brown is in Barcelona or not, either of those two mutually exclusive (contradictory) facts that occur will make $(f) \vee X$ true.

Moreover, the generality of authors seems not to have realized that Gettier could have better chosen the option "is not in Barcelona," and his argumentation would not need to invoke "the sheerest coincidence," making it much more likely to be true by chance. Although it would still lack logical validity.

Moving from (f) to $(f) \vee X$ is to commit to a valid tautological generalization, where X can include any proposition. However, whatever specifies X and makes it true, turning it into a constant proposition that makes a new sentence of the form $(f) \vee X$ true, is chosen by Gettier as an oracle would, as if it were the one meant to convert $(f) \vee X$ into a justified true belief.

Either Smith does not believe that B (or that $\neg B$) occurs in fact, or he does. But if he does, then he has an unjustified belief, judging that considering anything that comes to mind gives him concrete knowledge of something. This leads us into a logical system where anything can be deduced, where any belief can be justified, an inconsistent system.

Smith has the general idea that necessarily one of those propositions is true and the others false. But he does not know which is which. And by Gettier specifying one of them post hoc, according to what has occurred in his presentation of reality, he is elaborating, in an oracular manner, a new more specific proposition (h) , which was not originally in either (f) or its entailed $(f) \vee X$ (from which (h) is derived, as well as (h^*) , or an infinite number of other potential specifications that can render it true).

In this case, Gettier omits to make explicit an intermediate action, the step towards $(f) \vee X$, from which he later deduces (g) , (h) , and (i) . Thus, we have that Smith believes that $(f) \vee X$ is true, justifiably, but also either

(ii') Smith really does NOT believe that (h) is true because Brown is in Barcelona;

or, if he does,

(iii') Smith is NOT justified in believing that (h) is true because Brown is in Barcelona.

Since in both cases he could also justifiably and at the same time believe that (h^*) is also true because Brown is not in Barcelona.

From the initial premise, Smith not only believes in the disjunction but also believes that the condition that makes the disjunction true is solely the part (f), regardless of whether part B is true or false. The oracle justifies: we said that one of the two things was going to happen, and it happened. The oracle is not univocal, but it treats the disjunction, even without specifying, as if it were a univocal proposition, as if it were one and only one of its specifications (adopted a posteriori), namely (h).

6. Gettier cases by other authors.

It is asserted that

In Gettier's cases, the justified true belief is inferred from a justified false belief. ... However, ... there are examples of Gettier cases that need involve no inference (Ichikawa, 2018).

And:

What distinguishes these cases from the preceding counterexamples to sufficiency is that, in them, there are no identifiable false tacit assumptions (Lycan 2006, p. 157).

Examples of such cases may be the following:

The Hindu Dharmottara asked:

Imagine that we are seeking water on a hot day. We suddenly see water, or so we think. In fact, we are not seeing water but a mirage, but when we reach the spot, we are lucky and find water right there under a rock. Can we say that we had genuine knowledge of water? The answer seems to be negative, for we were just lucky (quoted by Dreyfus 1997, p. 292).

On the other hand, the philosopher Pedro de Mantua posed:

Let it be assumed that Plato is next to you and you know him to be running, but you mistakenly believe that he is Socrates, so that you firmly believe that Socrates is running. However, let it be so that Socrates is in fact running in Rome; however, you do not know this (quoted by Boh 1985, p. 95)

Chisholm presents the following case:

A person takes there to be a sheep in the field and does so under conditions which are such that, when under those conditions a person takes there to be a sheep in the field, then it is evident for that person that there is a sheep in the field. The person, however, has mistaken a dog for a sheep and so what he sees is not a sheep at all.

Nevertheless it happens that there is a sheep in another part of the field. Hence, the proposition that there is a sheep in the field will be one that is both true and evident and it will also be one that the person accepts. But the situation does not warrant our saying that the person knows that there is a sheep in the field (Chisholm, 1977, p. 93).

In all these cases, what is believed, the proposition (1) that is formulated, refers to a specific location and to a specific object that is being considered (the mirage, Plato, or the dog); and our possible knowledge relates only to that location and that object. In this regard, by the very nature of the argument, we are confirmed that we had a non-true belief.

It is reasoning in an oracle-like manner if one wishes to substantiate the idea that one had a justified belief, with a new proposition (2), by generalizing to (2), to the *ambiguous*, the proposition (1), which allows encompassing, in addition to the *specific* location (1), also the x points in the surroundings, or even from distant places, like Rome.

And then (2) is specified toward another newly interpreted proposition (3) ($\neq(1)$) that is indeed true, by incorporating a posteriori the location or the specific object $\neg(1)$ where the favorable fact occurs; even if it is different from the exact location or object corresponding to (1), to which reference was made. Thus, we make that generalization true. This generalization, in reality, also becomes false if we replace its variable with the logical constant of specification (1), which expresses in each of the cited cases the belief that each of the proposed individuals has. Thus, (1) is false, (3) is true; and (2) is ambiguous, and there is no reason to confuse it either with (1) or with (3).

7. The limits in the justification of a belief.

Similar to the cited cases, Goldman presents the following situation:

Henry is driving in the countryside with his son ... "That's a cow," says Henry, "That's a tractor," "That's a silo," "That's a barn," etc. ... Each object is fully in view, Henry has excellent eyesight, and he has enough time to look at them reasonably carefully, since there is little traffic to distract him. ... Suppose we are told that, unknown to Henry, the district he has just entered is full of papier-mâché facsimiles of barns. These facsimiles look from the road exactly like barns, but are really just façades ... The object he sees is a genuine barn. But if the object on that site were a facsimile, Henry would mistake it for a barn. Given this new information, we would be strongly inclined to withdraw the claim that Henry knows the object is a barn. ... It is accidental that Henry is right about its being a barn. So we withdraw our knowledge attribution (Goldman, pp. 772-773).

There is another change of constants here. Henry refers to barn g , and his belief pertains to it. But Goldman shifts to the variable x , all the facsimiles in the

area, and then specifies regarding each of these as constants h, i, j , etc., each of which is merely a facsimile, except precisely for the construction relevant to Henry's belief, which is g .

There are two ways in which a belief can be justified: either by experience or by being a logical truth.

The two cases presented by Gettier aim to represent beliefs justified through logical truths.

In the other cases mentioned here, it is only possible to justify the belief based on *experience*. This is why "they do not need to include any inference."

There are two kinds of experience: direct and indirect. The cases of mirages, Plato, the false sheep, and Henry can be directly verified (justified or denied). One can simply go to where the mirage supposedly was, look clearly at the other corridor, get close enough to the false sheep, or inspect the barn more closely.

But they can also be justified based on what is described by the authors of these cases (except in the case of the mirage, as regarding mirages in the desert a subject might believe they are frequent, and thus seeing is required to believe), indirectly, by *induction*, whether such researchers notice it or not: without looking clearly, without getting close enough, or without inspecting more carefully.

This can only occur based on previous experiences, when, for example, one knows that Socrates is the person who frequently tends to run alongside, or that cases of false sheep are much less common in the real world than true sheep; or that the same applies to false and true barns.

Following Goldman's approach, Henry does not believe his belief is justified as a logical truth. Or if he does believe it, then his belief is not justified. Thus, Henry can validly believe that his belief is justified by experience. However, Henry does not exhaust the available means for direct empirical verification, as he does not conduct, e.g., a more meticulous examination. Thus, either Henry does not believe his belief is justified as a sufficiently direct verification; or, if he believes it, then his belief is not justified.

Henry is left only with indirect experience. And if he is asked about the justification of his belief, it is only validly justifiable that he recognizes that it is based on induction from his prior experience, lacking depth in direct verification.

This, which we can call a relative *deficit of direct corroboration*, is what is compensated for by resorting to induction, consciously or subconsciously.

Goldman only selects the points that are relevant to his argument, those of the countryside through which Henry travels, without taking into account the entire *universe* of barns that he might previously know, directly or by reference, where what predominates abundantly are real barns and not the façades that simulate them.

What is accidental, primarily, is that Henry is passing through one of the scarce places in his country and the world where facsimiles prevail. And considering that his judgment presupposes what he knows about the vast majority of barn façades, which correspond to real constructions, then he was correct not by chance, but because, in reality, based on induction from his prior knowledge, that was the most probable situation.

This last point is the only thing that can lead the author to think that Henry's belief is justified. And it allows for not demanding, to consider it thus, that he would

have had to conduct a direct empirical verification, a more detailed inspection, readily available, of the barn.

In this case, Goldman falls into what Tversky and Kahneman call a *bias*, a cognitive illusion (that of base rate neglect) (see Tversky 1982). By not considering in his argument the *base rate frequency* across the entire relevant universe of what Henry knows about barns, to justify or not Henry's belief; but only to a small part of that universe, the subset of false barns in that area.

What would have been accidental as a fact in this matter, regarding his prior knowledge universe, is that the barn Henry thought he saw was a facsimile; that his belief about that specific barn did not match reality and, therefore, he was mistaken.

In summary, Goldman can only implicitly assume (to assert that there is a justified belief) that Henry makes an induction, and issues his judgment taking the base rate from his prior knowledge universe A. But then, surreptitiously, he shifts from base frequency to a universe B, a subset of A that is much more limited; and on this logically invalid change, he grounds his argument to later deny the existence of knowledge.

Goldman makes the leap from "There is one and only one universe A" to the syntactic generalization "There exists some universe X" and from there to the substitutive specification "There exists a universe X=B," thereby conflating the necessary and sufficient conditions for justified belief (those of Henry's prior knowledge universe about barns) with the *necessary but not sufficient* conditions (the consideration of only false barns in that area).

8. Conclusions.

Linda Zagzebski establishes a procedure to construct Gettier cases, which she considers makes them *inescapable*:

Start with a case of justified (or warranted) false belief. Make the element of justification (warrant) strong enough for knowledge, but make the belief false ... due to some element of luck. Now emend the case by adding another element of luck, only this time an element which makes the belief true after all. The second element must be independent of the element of warrant so that the degree of warrant is unchanged (Zagzebski 1994, p. 69).

However, there is additionally a deeper, *fallacious structure* of the procedure, the oracular, whose recognition allows one *to escape* the Gettier problems. And it involves the transition from "There is one and only one" to simply "There exists," and then, without justification, to the inconsistent change of constant, treating a belief sentence as if it were a simple sentence; confusing the necessary and sufficient conditions with the necessary but not sufficient ones.

That is to say:

1. Begin with an expression (1) referring to an object, a fact, a place, or a determined universe of discourse, containing a logical constant *c*, *concrete*, referring to any of those aspects, with its specific necessary and sufficient conditions for justified belief.
2. *Generalize* the same expression to a new expression (2), *ambiguous*, using a logical variable *x* instead of the constant, suppressing some of those necessary conditions.

3. *Reinterpret*, without logical justification, the general expression (2) with a new logical constant *d* replacing the variable *x*, that is different and contradictory to *c*, referring to an object, a fact, a place, or a *specific* universe that fits post hoc to the situation that actually occurs; but that does not meet some suppressed necessary condition. Thus generating a newly interpreted expression (3), while confusing (3) with (2).

This turns Gettier-style reasoning into a logically inconsistent, sibylline-type argument.

alejandromatusunfe020@gmail.com

References.

- (1) Ayer, A. J., 1956, *The Problem of Knowledge* (London: Macmillan).
- (2) Boh, Ivan, 1985, "Belief, Justification and Knowledge: Some Late Medieval Epistemic Concerns", in *Journal of the Rocky Mountain Medieval and Renaissance Association*, 6: 87–103. Quoted by Ichikawa 2018.
- (3) Chisholm, Roderick, 1957, *Perceiving: A Philosophical Study* (New York: Cornell University Press).
- (4) ————1977, *Theory of Knowledge*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- (5) Dretske, Fred, May 1971, "Conclusive reasons", in *Australasian Journal of Philosophy*. 49 (1), 1–22.
doi:10.1080/00048407112341001.
- (6) Dreyfus, George B.J, 1997, *Recognizing Reality: Dharmakirti's Philosophy and its Tibetan Interpretations* (Albany, New York: Suny Press). Quoted by Ichikawa 2018.
- (7) Gettier, Edmund L. 1 June 1963. "Is Justified True Belief Knowledge?", *Analysis*, 23 (6): 121–123. doi:10.1093/analys/23.6.121.
- (8) Goldman, Alvin I., 1976, "Discrimination and Perceptual Knowledge", in *The Journal of Philosophy*, 73(20), pp. 771–791. doi:10.2307/2025679.
- (9) Herodotus, 1975, *Histories*, Books I-II, (Harvard University Press and William Heinemann Ltd., Loeb Classical Library).
- (10) Ichikawa, Jonathan, Jenkins y Matthias Steup, Verano 2018, "The Analysis of Knowledge", in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, Edward N. Zalta (ed.).
URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2018/entries/knowledge-analysis/>>.
- (11) Lycan, William. G., 2006, "On the Gettier Problem problem", in *Epistemology Futures*, S. Hetherington (ed.) (Oxford: Oxford University Press), pp. 148-168.
- (12) Nozick, Robert, 1981, *Philosophical Explanations* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press).

(13) Plato, 2005, *Meno and other dialogues*, (New York: Oxford University Press).

(14) Plato, 2015, *Theaetetus and Sophist* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press).

(15) Russell Bertrand, Oct. 1905, On denoting. *Mind*, New Series, Vol. 14, No. 56, pp. 479-493. Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/mind/XIV.4.479>.

(16) Tversky, Amos y Daniel Kahneman, 1982, "Evidential impact of base rates", in Tversky, Kahneman, y P. Slovic, ed., *Judgment under uncertainty: Heuristics and Biases* (New York: Cambridge University Press).

(17) Zagzebski, Linda, 1994, "The Inescapability of Gettier Problems", in *The Philosophical Quarterly*, 44 (174): 65–73, Blackwell Publishing.
[doi:10.2307/2220147](https://doi.org/10.2307/2220147).